

virescens Dist. at 2 insects per plant 24 h after spraying. Control plants were sprayed with 0.1% detergent solution alone. Two replications of 10 plants each were maintained for each treatment. Number of plants infected and incubation period were recorded.

All plant extracts tested reduced tungro infection. Seed extract of *T. terrestris* was most effective in reducing tungro infection, followed by leaf extracts of *V. negundo* var. *purpurascens*, *Catharanthus roseus*, and *Aloe vera*, and stem extract of *Cissus quadrangularis* (see table). The same extracts significantly prolonged incubation. Plants whose extracts were tested for tungro control:

Andrographis paniculata (Burm.f) Wall ex Nees.

Agave americana Linn.

Catharanthus roseus (L.) G. Don.

Cascabela thevetia (L.) Lippold.

Optimal stage to apply Rabcide 4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide for rice blast (BI) control

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We studied the optimum stages for treating rice with Rabcide (4, 5, 6, 7-tetrachlorophthalide), an organophosphorus pesticide, in 1989 and 1990.

Basmati 385 was transplanted at 31 d after seeding in 2- x 4-m plots. Nine treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. *Pyricularia grisea* (= *P.*

Effect of some plant extracts on tungro infection in rice.^a

Source of extract	Reduction (%) of infection over control	Incubation period (d)
<i>Tribulus terrestris</i>	45 (42.13) a	12.6 a
<i>Vitex negundo purpurascens</i>	41 (39.82) a	12.4 a
<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i>	34 (35.70) b	12.2 a
<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	34 (35.67) b	12.1 a
<i>Aloe vera</i>	34 (35.68) b	11.8 a
Control	0 (0.99) c	10.4 b
LSD (P = 0.10)	3	0.8

^a Figures in parentheses are arc sine transformed values. In a column, figures followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

Calotropis gigantea (L.) R. Br.

Tridax procumbens Linn.

Cylindropuntia ramosissima (Engler) Kunth.

Cassia auriculata Linn.

Carica papaya Linn.

Cleome gynandra Linn.

Parthenium hysterophorus Linn.

Ipomoea staphylinia Roem and Schultus.

oryzae) was inoculated at 10, 20, 30, and 40 d after transplanting. Rabcide was applied at 0.5 g/8 m².

Grain yield was highest with spraying at early and late booting and after flowering, and at primary infection (see table). Yield was lowest with no treatment and with one spraying after flowering. Neck BI was lowest when the crop was sprayed three times and highest with only one spraying at early booting. Results indicate a direct relationship between disease incidence and yield.

One application of Rabcide, at primary infection, controlled BI adequately. Three applications gave the highest yield, but took three times as much chemical and labor.

Grain yield and broken necks of rice following Rabcide application against rice blast.^a

Spraying schedule	Grain yield (kg/100 plants)		Neck blast/100 Panicles in 1990
	1989	1990	
At primary infection	1.9	1.9	2.5
At early booting	1.6	1.6	9.5
At late booting	1.6	1.6	4.2
After flowering	1.5	1.4	7.2
At early booting and after flowering	1.8	1.7	3.2
At early booting and late flowering	1.6	1.6	4.2
At late booting and after flowering	1.6	1.6	4.2
At early and late booting and after flowering	2.0	2.1	1.5
No spray	1.2	1.2	17.0

^a Each figure is a mean of 4 counts.

Ipomoea carnea Jacq.

Croton bonplandianum Bail.

Euphorbia tirucalli Linn.

Jatropha glandulifera Roxb.

Pedilanthus tithymaloides (L.) Poier.

Synadenium grandii Hook.

Ocimum tenuiflorum Linn.

Aloe vera Linn.

Urginea indica Kunth.

Ficus racemosa Linn.

Ficus benghalensis Linn. var. *benghalensis* King.

Acacia nilotica (L) Willd. ex. Del. subsp. *indica* (Benth) Brepan.

Areca catechu Linn.

Antigonon leptopus Hook & Arn.

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb.

Datura metal Linn.

Vitex negundo Linn. *negundo*.

Vitex negundo var. *purpurascens* Sivaranjan & Mold.

Cissus quadrangularis Linn.

Tribulus terrestris Linn. ■

Integrated pest management – insects

Life history of two braconid parasitoids of rice leafhopper (LF) in the laboratory

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Two braconids, *Cardiochiles philippinensis* (Fig. 1a) and *Macrocentrus philippinensis* (Fig. 1b), are the dominant parasitoids of LF larvae in the Philippines. We studied their life history under 26 ± 3°C temperature and 75 ± 10% relative humidity.

Newly emerged parasitoid adults were paired and placed in an oviposition cage (23 cm in diameter x 60 cm high) with 20 3d-instar larvae of *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* on potted plants. Host larvae were replaced daily until the parasitoid died.

Parasitized larvae were reared on potted rice plants for 7 d, then transferred individually into test tubes (16 mm in diameter x 150 mm high). Fresh rice leaves were provided every other day